

Cases for teaching and learning assessment planning: a study in the perception of teachers and students from two Brazilian universities

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Abstract

When applied in the classroom, the teaching cases, generate an opportunity, considering the aspects and particularities involved, to study the assessment planning of learning with the adoption of this methodology. The work aims to describe the planning process in the application of learning assessment when adopting the teaching case method in administration courses. This is a multicase and exploratory study, with a qualitative approach, in two federal institutions of higher education in Brazil. The data collection instruments consisted of conducting semi-structured interviews with 10 teachers and 53 students who had already gone through subjects that had the application of the teaching case, with the sample being defined based on the theoretical saturation criterion. The technique for discussing the data was content analysis, also supported by the Iramuteq® software, adopting, a priori, the following theoretical categories: forms of assessment (Fernandes & Fialho, 2012) and time of assessment (Tormena & Figueiredo, 2010). The results showed that when comparing responses of teachers and students surveyed that students and a part of teachers value the form of assessment adopted, especially the students' discussions in groups (Hoffman, 2014). Another part of the teachers uses the assessment based on an expected response pattern (Roesch, 2007), whether it is defined a priori (Albertoni & Silva, 2018) or made more flexible. Regarding the evaluation moment, the teachers elaborate the teaching plan and present it to the students. Students corroborate with teachers when they cite group discussion as a form of assessment, as well as report the need to make a decision to find solutions to the proposed problem (Graham, 2010, Soares et al. 2019). This work is concluded by understanding, although summative assessment methods are used when teaching cases are applied, formative assessment is an option in the planning of useful tools in the development of new skills.

Keywords: Teaching Case Method; Learning Assessment; Administration Teaching

1 Introduction

The worker's pace of work makes his practice less reflective (Mintzberg, 2010). This reality is also a reflection of teaching historically based only on reproduction and had to transform itself so that the professional develops skills of understanding, critical analysis and reflection in a competitive market (Suaia, 2013, Kakouris, 2015). In this context, Silva, Oliveira and Mota (2013) highlight the case method for teaching as one of the strategies of the learning system in action for the teaching of administration. From the practice of methodologies such as the case for teaching, it is necessary to plan and apply other forms of evaluation that can cover weaknesses of the methods evaluated until the applicable knowledge (Mansur & Alves, 2018). On this subject, Consolaro (2005) assumes that the learning objectives planned by the teacher must be intertwined with the assessment, student development and emphasizing the quality of individualized advancement. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account the importance of planning and carrying out the work proposed by the teacher.

2 Case method for teaching and the learning assessment planning process

Gil (2004) conceptualizes the case method for teaching as reports used and studied by individuals or groups to solve problems and make decisions. For Araujo, Rejowsky and Leal (2012), it is a methodology that describes a real problem faced by a person in the organization, usually presented from the point of view of the decision maker, in order to take this situation to a learning context, inviting people and students to reflect and position themselves in the context presented. For the student to be able to position himself and put himself in the role of the decision maker to find the solution to the problem presented, it is necessary that he has sufficient theoretical foundation to apply theory to practice and solve the problem presented, avoiding the risk of being based on 'beliefs' (Christense, 1987).

Miranda (2008), when studying the evaluation of learning through teaching cases in graduate courses in business, describes the learning process in three stages: a) individual preparation of the student: familiarization reading, complementary readings, diagnosis of the problem, development of alternatives, definition of criteria, proposal of solution; b) group discussion (Mendes, Trevisan & Souza, 2016), where there is an opportunity to debate individual positions and advance the level of understanding; c) plenary discussion, where the understanding of the case develops.

Therefore, it is necessary to take into account the importance of planning and carrying out the work proposed by the teacher. One of the ways to carry out this planning is from the elaboration of the teaching plan built at the beginning of the discipline (Silva, Santos & Paixão, 2014). The plan helps the teacher to organize the necessary resources for the classes and favors the monitoring of the activities that will be developed (Tormena & Figueiredo, 2010). This avoids improvisation, facilitates the integration of students with learning experiences, so that the student's vision is broadened, cooperative, participatory and this develops autonomy in learning (Sasaki, 1997, Nogaro, 2018).

When carrying out the planning of his classes, the teacher chooses the evaluation method he will use, decisively influencing the way the students will direct their studies. This choice will serve as a parameter for the student to plan the time he will dedicate to his studies, define the contents and priorities to be learned and determine his degree of engagement in academic activities (Silva, 2015).

Luckesi (2011) also states that the evaluation of learning will only be successful if in its planning there is clarity in what it aims to achieve, if it shows the commitment and investment of those who perform the act of evaluating and if it contributes to the investigation and the transformation of pedagogical practices. The author states that the evaluation must be procedural, dynamic and constructive in order to subsidize the teacher so that his / her action is as appropriate as possible, prevailing the student's learning.

3 Methodology

This is a multiple and exploratory case study, with a qualitative analysis approach. In this perspective, the present study investigates the perception of professors and students at UFRN and UFPB who use the case method for teaching in their disciplines. Ten teachers from the two institutions were interviewed. In addition, the second group consisted of fifty-three students from UFRN and UFPB. Data processing was carried out through content analysis, where the categories of analysis emerged from theoretical support: forms of assessment (Fernandes & Fialho, 2012) and time of assessment (Tormena & Figueiredo, 2010). Finally, for data analysis, a reading of the comments transcribed in the interview was carried out, aiming at coding and grouping the text units - in order to carry out a more assertive analysis of the teachers' comments and in relation to the students, the Iramuteq® software was used. to assist in the analysis of responses and contemplate the objectives to which the present study set out.

4 Analysis of Results

In order to maintain the anonymity of the respondents, a codification was established for the subjects and their speeches, distinguishing them between participants from Rio Grande do Norte and Paraíba. Thus, the "P" code represents that the respondent is the teacher. The acronyms RN were added to the end of the teachers' codes to facilitate the identification of teachers in Rio Grande do Norte and teachers in Paraíba - PB, varying between PRN and PPB.

For the students, other codes were defined, where "A" means that it was a testimony from a student. Like the teachers, the acronyms of the states, where Rio Grande do Norte - RN and Paraíba - PB, were also added to the students' codes, varying between ARN and APB. The question applied with teachers and students had the objective of identifying how the learning assessment planning occurred in the application of cases for teaching in the discipline taught. The results of the interviews carried out showed that all professors interviewed at UFRN and UFPB plan, in some way, the evaluation process applied in the classroom. When affirming that they plan the evaluation, it is possible to perceive as one of the contributions of this research that, according to the speech of the teachers, they carry out the planning in two ways: the first group values in their testimonies that they prefer to plan their evaluation considering the forms of assessment that will be applied in the classroom. In the other group, the teachers focus on the moment or period when they will apply the assessment, thinking and planning each activity at the beginning of the discipline, that is, before it happens.

In this sense, the studies by Zanon, Kailer and Althaus (2017) state that in order to use evaluation strategies well, it is necessary, first of all, to plan teaching situations. Complementing this thought, Tormena and Figueiredo (2010) point out in their research that they are the actions previously planned that will improve the performance of the teacher in the classroom when applying the assessment. In relation to the first group, as reported in the teachers' statements, they value the forms of evaluation in their assessment planning when they apply cases for teaching - that is, they did not detail the period of time in which they planned the evaluations, but described the moment of the application of the evaluation.

On this subject, research by Depresbiteres (2010) points out that it is important that the form of evaluation is chosen according to the objectives that one wishes to achieve. In the same sense, the studies by Fernandes and Fialho (2012) state that, in general, teachers use different forms of assessment, not limited to tests. Continuing with the forms of assessment reported by the respondents, another group of teachers was identified, five subjects, one from UFRN and four from UFPB, who carry out evaluations based on student participation, when they are discussing in small groups, and then expand the debate for a large group discussion, according to the excerpts from the statements below.

"[...] then students can discuss in groups and then we take a larger approach with the whole room and then I make theoretical connections and clarify some concepts" (Prn2F1). "[...] we do the discussion in small groups and then do the discussion in the plenary" (Ppb10F1). "[...] they divide it into groups, they debate the answers in groups and then, they get the whole group together so that we can arrive more or less at a common denominator, more or less" (Ppb6F1) "[...] I never worked individually, I worked in a group" (Ppb8F1). "At first, the participation of students and their involvement in small groups, right? When we separate the class, go to the groups and pass the questions, pass the case and pass the questions. So I evaluate the interaction between them, you see the participation of everyone, a circle between the groups observing the interaction, participation and contribution, you know. This is a first step. In the second moment, it makes a large group and then again I evaluate the general participation group by group and individually in the resolution of issues "(Ppb9F1).

In the reports presented by the teachers, it is noticed that they carry out activities that involve student participation, both in small groups and in plenary discussion, so that the student himself can interact, argue and discuss the solutions of the case and learn during the debates. The excerpts from the speeches corroborate the studies by Miranda (2008) who point out that in discussions in small groups and in plenary there is an opportunity to debate individual positions and advance the level of complete and detailed understanding of the case. In this way, when the teacher describes the student's participation in the discussions, using this to evaluate him, according to what the studies present, he helps the student to position himself in the discussions,

to place himself as the decision maker, reflecting on the problem and understanding the situation presented. Another format of evaluation planning found in the research results was to carry out based on an expected response pattern. In this research, this evaluation format is subdivided into two groups of teachers, namely: one that is based on the response pattern defined in the teaching notes and the other that values the same response pattern, but that this can be made more flexible from of the new solutions for the case found by the groups of students. Thus, the research subject who relies on the response pattern defined in the teaching notes, a professor from UFRN, reports in his speech that

"I carry out the evaluation based on the response that the students give to the case, establishing standards for the expected response" (Prn3F1).

The teacher expects the student to answer the questions present in the case and to evaluate them according to the response patterns that are in the teaching notes. Students should realize, according to the studies by Roesch (2007) and Marion and Marion (2006), the possible solutions to the problem reported in the case, since there is not only one answer to the dilemma presented and choose the one, he believes to be the most suitable.

It is understood, therefore, that there may be solutions pointed out by students that are not included in the answer keys, that is, students can give a different solution than the one the teacher already expects. However, there was no evidence in this professor's speech that he was open so that, perhaps, some solution would be different from those that were previously established. The excerpt of the teacher's speech is in accordance with the studies by Roesch (2007), when he points out that the teaching notes must contain questions for the discussion of the case and must be well formulated to arouse the interest of the discussion and stimulate individual and group learning. In addition, research by Albertoni and Silva (2018) states that the author must specify alternatives for the analysis of the case, presenting the theory used to substantiate the case and that will serve as a basis to guide the answers to the questions proposed in the classroom.

Just like the research subject Prn3 in his F1 speech, there is one more teacher who also evaluates based on a response pattern, but who is flexible to accept the different solutions given by students different from those shown in the teaching notes. It is worth noting that in the case method theories, no record was found that talks about this flexibility in the responses, as reported by the subject Prn4 in his F1 speech below. Therefore, this subcategory emerged from the data collected and analyzed in this research. Thus, the expected response pattern serves as a general parameter in the evaluation process, although it does not impede the innovation capacity of the group of students, allowing an opening in the evaluation process to contemplate, in addition to the response options suggested in the teaching notes, other additional elements that were considered and discussed by the group, since

"There is no punctual answer, there are some indicators that we will follow to try to guide the rationality of the decision. But eventually this is open, the solution that the group may be able to refer is completely different or different from the referral of another group". (Prn4F1)

The teacher reports that different solutions given by the groups are expected. In this way, assessment is not compromised and allows the student to seek, even, the resolution of the case from contents seen in other disciplines, in addition to those used in the case. The teacher, therefore, uses the indicators in a flexible way, that is, if perhaps a student or group resolves the case differently from what he expects, this solution may be valid. Still in relation to planning based on the forms of assessment, another subcategory found in the study and in the testimony of a professor at UFRN was that he conducts the assessment based on a self-assessment he adopts with his students.

"E também temos a auto avaliação deles ao final do semestre do que temos visto dessa área, então a gente também tem de certa forma essa avaliação. Então a gente também solicita que eles avaliem, deem o feedback deles, tanto no momento do caso, que tem aquela reação imediata, né, que a gente chama de avaliação da avaliação, como também pra avaliar no final o que, o que é que na aplicação desses casos contribuem para a aprendizagem deles" (Prn1F1).

Different from the perception of this previous group of teachers, - in the second group, focusing on the moment of the evaluation, two professors from UFPB carry out the previous planning of the evaluation in a

"[...] we discussed in groups and then discussed with the rest of the teams about the case for teaching and there were also those where each group, each team, we received a different case study." (A19F2)

"At first she passed the cases on to teaching, she posted on SIGAA, then she did a previous reading and everyone arrived to discuss in the groups and then in the group." (A20F2)

"[...] most of the teachers gave the case for teaching in writing for us to do the reading. [...] debated in groups and then we presented one or two solutions or to the whole room in which we could discuss." (A21F2)

"[...] he asked us to get together in a group, read the case and show how we would solve that situation." (A29F2)

"[...] the teacher sent him the case, before the class, so that we could do his reading and study, that is, during the class, a dynamic reading was usually done. [...] the application was generally divided into groups. we were placed in groups based on the number of students in the class." (A34F2)

"[...] the teacher gave the text with the case, a week before, then we read individually, answered some questions and then in the classroom we formed groups, discussed the case, answered the questions in groups, sometimes some disagreed with the other's opinion, but it was very interesting." (A36F2)

"First, the teacher passed the case on for us to read, usually at home, in the classroom, divided it into groups, to discuss the issues of the case, because the case always ends with some questions to answer a topic, and it was debated in groups, then the teacher resumed, discussing in general what the results were and answering the questions." (A44F2)

The words cited by the students are very related, that is, when they spoke in a group, they immediately cited discussion, as did the terms debate and reading. Students report the discussion of cases in small groups to answer the proposed questions and then discuss in the large group the various solutions found. The excerpts from the speeches are in agreement with the findings of Cobb and Yackel (1996) who state that one of the ways to accompany students is group work, which promotes interaction between students when they need to negotiate meanings and interpretations in search of consensual or compatible forms of understanding in and through social interactions. Another term mentioned by the students and that is present in the word cloud is "solution", according to the statements.

" Usually he passes a data to us with a problem for us to solve, we usually discuss these activities in groups, try to find the solutions, the most likely ways, I don't know, within what we know and formalize with the teacher and he evaluates it later. " (A9F3)

"I read all the texts that we had to use as the basis for the activity where we were going to answer a question based on a real case that really happened. And based on that, we would have to provide a solution that does not exist right or wrong, but a correct answer based on each situation." (A13F3)

"He brought some teaching cases for us to analyze and find the most viable solution to the company's problem." (A24F3)

"[...] the teacher delivered the paper with the case for teaching, you know, and asked us to give an opinion, how we would solve that situation, what would be the most viable solution." (A28F1)

"[...] she divided the class in two and each of the classes went to defend a different idea looking for the points, pros or cons, or defending each aspect of the case presented to find the most appropriate solution to solve the problem. " (A43F1)

The students report that the teacher, when applying the methodology of the case for teaching, asks them for possible solutions to the problem of the presented company, leaving the students to occupy the position of company administrator, solving the problem, bringing the reality of the company closer to the classroom of class. It is noticed that the teachers accepted the solutions presented by the students, even if they were not the same ones that were suggested in the teaching notes of the case at the moment when statements like "we would have to give a solution that does not exist right or wrong, but a correct answer based on each situation.", "find the most viable solution to the company's problem ", " find the most appropriate solution to solve the problem. "

The statements corroborate the studies by Graham (2010), Clemente Junior (2012) and Soares et al. (2019) for those who do not have a single correct answer for the teaching case, even allowing the confrontation of opinions between the students who propose the solutions. Another term that appeared in the word cloud related to planning was "decision", which is directly related to "solution", according to the statements.

"[...] the teacher put a type of activity at home, for the student to develop in the decision-making process within the scope of the Administration." (A29F4)

"So you had a storm of ideas that later you had to combine them all and make a conclusion from it, make a decision within different ways of analyzing, different ways of thinking." (A46F4)

"[...] we needed to decide this, he gave us eight days, gave all the data, the details and we each needed to take his opinion, what he would do, what was his decision as an administrator." (A53F4)

Students affirm that they need to make decisions to find solutions to the problem presented in the case, which corroborates the research by Spricigo (2014) when he affirms that methodologies, such as the case for teaching, that are based on real situations are powerful to develop in students' skills and abilities related to decision making and problem solving.

In the same sense, the observations of Soares et al. (2019) point out that the teaching cases describe realistic and sufficiently complex situations and problems that have multiple skillful decisions to solve problems, engaging students in "real world" problems, promoting good discussions in search of understanding about what would be the best decision to be taken to solve the problems proposed in the case.

Even though it was not mentioned by many students, but considering the context in which the students answer the planning question, narrating about the way the teachers apply the case, a term that can be analyzed related to the first question of the data collection instrument of the students. students is "experience", according to the statements.

"It was an interesting experience, because we had not yet passed and even that motivated some students to write, in the following period, their course completion papers in this format of teaching cases." (A43F2)

"[...] the teacher already had an experience of applying cases, including he also guided students to build cases for teaching and the experience was very positive because the students were motivated to write cases on the tcc." (A47F1)

The students report on the positive experience of having the cases for teaching in the classroom and that, after that, some students were motivated to write a case as a course conclusion work. The student's interest in the experience of the teaching case may be linked to the fact that it is a different methodology from the conventional teaching methods that he is used to dealing with in most disciplines. In the case of teaching, he occupies the position of manager to make decisions related to real problems, an opportunity to get closer to professional practice. The fact that students are interested in building cases for the end-of-course work may be related to the student having lived some experience that serves to build a case. In addition, the methodology brings students closer to professional practice and allows them to solve in the classroom issues they experience in the job market, as pointed out by Soares et al. (2019) It is noticed that only UFPB students report the experience of having colleagues who choose the construction of a case as an end-of-course work. This is due to the Administration course at this university having among the options of final works the cases for teaching, according to UFPB (2016).

4.1 Summary of research results with teachers and students

Regarding evaluation planning, the teachers' response is divided into two large groups: the majority, nine of them, answered the question by citing the forms of evaluation that they perform in the classroom when applying cases for teaching. These forms of assessment included the participation of students in groups, the correction of case responses according to a defined standard (which can be a priori or made more flexible) and assessment through students' self-assessment. Only one teacher reported that he carries out the planning in a previous and systematized way. When comparing this question with the students' answers, they all talked about how the teacher applies the assessment of learning and the majority cited the participation of students in the

groups as a means of evaluating, confirming what was said by the majority of teachers. This demonstrates, comparing the general result of students and teachers, that the planning of the evaluation system includes a participation of the groups, being adopted by most of the teachers in the classroom, although there are some different forms of evaluation mentioned by only a few students: solving the problem of the case and making a decision.

It is noticed that this type is not in the forms mentioned by the teachers, because the solutions are found in groups, therefore, this way of evaluating is inserted in the participation of the students in the groups mentioned by the teachers. It is also understood that decision-making is also inserted in the discussion of students in groups, so this item can also be inserted in this form of assessment mentioned by teachers.

It is understood that the students mentioned the ways of evaluating in a more detailed way because they do not have the planning and evaluation experience that the teacher has. For the teacher, evaluating the student's participation involves verifying the solutions given to the case, observing the student's position as a decision maker, but this does not need to be detailed because thinking and structuring his classes and, consequently, evaluations is an activity present in the teacher's daily life, while the student does not have this practice and for that reason he details his response regarding the performance of the activity. The students also reported on the positive experience of participating in moments when teaching cases are applied, to the point that some students choose to build a teaching case in their course completion work.

Despite being mentioned by a small part of the students, the positive experience demonstrates the students' interest in using active teaching methodologies, such as the case for teaching, and to know the method in more depth, resulting in the construction of cases for work end of course. On the other hand, it is understood that, because it was mentioned by few students, this positive experience did not attract the attention of teachers to the point of being present in their answers.

5 Conclusion

This demonstrates, comparing the general result of students and teachers, that the planning of the evaluation system includes a participation of the groups, being adopted by most of the teachers in the classroom, although there are some different forms of evaluation mentioned by only a few students: solving the problem of the case and making a decision. It is noticed that this type is not in the forms mentioned by the teachers, because the solutions are found in groups, therefore, this way of evaluating is inserted in the participation of the students in the groups mentioned by the teachers. It is also understood that decision-making is also inserted in the discussion of students in groups, so this item can also be inserted in this form of assessment mentioned by teachers. It is concluded that teachers use summative and formative assessment methods in teaching cases, assisting in the professional training of students.

6 References

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